

Table 2. Yields of promising coarse-grained Indian rice varieties at the Agricultural Research Stations at Baghlan and Jalalabad, 1970-80.

Variety	Trials (no.)	Av yield (t/ha)		Increase over local variety	
		Indian variety	Local variety (LUK)	t/ha	%
<i>Baghlan</i>					
IET400	3	7.9	4.2	3.7	87
CR75-8	3	5.8	4.1	1.7	41
CR10-114	4	7.4	4.0	3.4	83
IET355	12	8.8	3.6	5.1	140
Padma	3	5.2	4.9	0.3	6
CR36-148	4	9.3	3.1	6.2	204
KH7194	3	10.2	3.6	5.7	180
K103-2-32	2	9.1	4.8	4.3	88
K103-2-3	2	7.4	4.8	2.6	53
K78-2	2	6.6	4.8	1.7	36
<i>Jalalabad</i>					
IET400	4	6.4	3.5	2.9	82
CR75-8	6	5.0	2.8	2.3	81
CR10-114	5	6.0	3.4	2.6	77
IET355	6	5.6	3.0	2.6	84
Padma	11	7.0	2.7	4.3	158
CR36-148	4	5.7	3.8	1.9	51
Jaya	2	4.6	3.8	0.8	22
CR44-1	6	5.8	3.2	2.9	80
CR115-76	2	6.1	3.7	2.4	65

Baghlan, average yields of Indian varieties ranged from 5.2 t/ha to 10.2 t/ha compared to 3.1-4.9 t/ha for local variety LUK, a yield difference of 6-204%. At Jalalabad, average yields of Indian varieties ranged from 4.6 t/ha to 7 t/ha compared to 2.7-3.8 t/ha for the local variety, a yield difference of 22-158%.

IET355 in the Northern Zone and Padma in the Eastern Zone were released as improved varieties in 1975. KH7194 is being tested on cultivators' fields in the Northern Zone to replace IET355. No variety has been identified to replace Padma in the Eastern Zone.

Varieties with 100- to 110-day durations in India are suitable for introduction in Afghanistan. Yield levels of Indian varieties were generally higher at Baghlan than at Jalalabad, perhaps because of the better environment in the Northern Zone. ■

CR1009, a promising rice cultivar

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CR1009 (IET5897), a promising long-duration rice cultivar evolved at the Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, is a cross between Pankaj and

Jagannath. It is semidwarf, with high tillering, medium-compact panicle, and white, short, bold grains.

The performance of CR1009 and of long-duration varieties Co 25, Co 40, and NLR 9672 was tested at PES, Tirurkuppam, during the samba season (August-January) from 1977-78 to 1980-81. CR1009 recorded a mean yield of 4.4 t/ha. Its duration was 151-165 days (Table 1).

CR1009 was also grown in farmers' fields in Thanjavur district during 1981-82 samba (Table 2). ■

Table 2. Performance of CR1009 in farmers' fields, Thanjavur district, India, 1981-82.

Farm size (ha)	Av grain yield (t/ha)
1.4	6.7
3.6	6.4
7.0	5.6

Table 1. Performance of CR1009 in samba season at Tamil Nadu, India.

Rice cultivar	1977-78		1978-79		1979-80		1980-81		Av Yield (t/ha)	Duration (days)
	Yield (t/ha)	Duration (days)	Yield (t/ha)	Duration (days)	Yield (t/ha)	Duration (days)	Yield (t/ha)	Duration (days)		
CR1009	5.7	151	4.3	162	4.4	155	3.0	165	4.35	151-165
Co 25	4.5	168	2.8	162	2.8	175	2.3	178	3.10	162-178
Co 40	5.9	162	3.7	150	3.9	165	2.5	178	4.00	150-178
NLR9672	NT	NT	3.7	151	4.1	165	2.1	175	3.30	151-175
<i>F</i> -test	Significant		Not significant		Significant		Not significant			
C.D. (<i>P</i> = 0.05)	1.30		-		0.46		0.65			

New rice varieties for Rajasthan

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Three new rice varieties — Chambal, BK190, and BK79 — were recently named by the University of Udaipur and

released for general cultivation in Rajasthan.

Chambal (IR8/NP130) is a dwarf, photoperiod-insensitive variety that matures in 135-140 days. Early seedling vigor is good and tillering ability is moderate. It has highly synchronized flowering, late leaf senescence, and stiff

straw. Grains are slightly longer than those of IR8 and protein content is higher. Average yield is 7.3 t/ha.

BK190 (R14/IR8) is an intermediate height, photoperiod-insensitive indica variety that matures in 145-155 days. Early seedling vigor is excellent and tillering capacity is good. Very sturdy